

Introduction to Research Data Management

Tip 1: Ensure Your Data, Software, and Hardware follow the FAIR Principles.

**Findable:
Searchable
by Others**

**Accessible:
A System
Exists to Grant
Access**

**Interoperable:
Can be
Integrated
with Other
Resources**

**Reusable:
Licenses are
Assigned to
Clarify Rights**

Tip 2: Plan Data Management for Each Stage of the Research Life Cycle

The Research Life Cycle

What Steps You can Take

Plan: Communicate with the univie research data management (RDM) team early and often. Draft a data management plan (DMP).

Collect and Prep: Make sure your data is safely stored. Establish a data collection pipeline and use tools like electronic lab notebooks.

Analyze: Keep clear records of your analyses and write well annotated code. Make good use of versioning tools.

Archive and Publish: Place your data, software, and hardware outputs in an appropriate repository.

Reuse: Ensure you outputs are all assigned a license that establishes clear expectations for data re-use. If you can, try to reuse data from others, while respecting ownership rights.

RDM Homepage

How to Reach the RDM Team

Anyone at univie can reach-out to the RDM team for help. You can reach us at rdm@univie.ac.at or find our webpage at rdm.univie.ac.at.